

**PILOTS for robotic INspection and maintenance
Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and
prototype applications**

Deliverable D5.4

Final version of advanced autonomous
functionalities for ground robots and crawlers

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Acronyms

Abbreviation	Explanation
A*	A graph traversal and path search algorithm (algorithm)
APE	Absolute Position Error
ArUco	A synthetic square marker composed of black and white squares
BIKE	Magnetic pipe inspection robot (robot)
BIM	Building Information Model
CART	Tunnel inspection robot (robot)
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
DC	Direct Current
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
gRCS	Generic Robot Control Station
I&M	Inspection and Maintenance
ICP	Iterative Closest Point (family of algorithms for point cloud registration)
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit (sensor)
IR	Infrared Radiation
IVP	Intelligence and Visualization Portal
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging (sensor)
LOAM	Lidar Odometry and Mapping
MPC	Model Predictive Control
MSF	Multi-sensor fusion
NUC	Next Unit of Computing
PID	Proportional–Integral–Derivative controller
PTP	Precision Time Protocol (protocol)
RGB-D	Optical camera (RGB) plus depth (D) sensing (sensor)
RISING	Refinery inspection robot (robot)
ROS	Robot Operating System (software)
RRT*	Optimized version of Rapidly-exploring Random Trees path planning
ORB	Oriented FAST (Features from Accelerated Segment Test) and rotated BRIEF (Binary Robust Independent Elementary Features)

SLAM	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (functionality)
TEB	Time Elastic Band (algorithm)
UAV	Unmanned aerial vehicle
UDP	User Datagram Protocol (protocol)
UGV	Unmanned ground vehicle (robot)

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope of the document

The main purpose of this document is to present the final version of the algorithms developed with respect to dexterous manipulation, advanced perception and intelligent navigation for autonomous inspection and maintenance for ground robots and crawlers. Moreover, the document describes how the final solutions have been improved from the beta versions described in D5.2 based on the experience from the initial test campaign. These functionalities are targeting firstly refineries with inspection both inside tanks and vessels as well as outside including manipulation of valves. Secondly, autonomous navigation in tunnels for ground vehicles is addressed. A common challenge in these scenarios is the lack of satellite coverage, which makes it necessary to find solutions for localization that do not rely on GNSS to enable autonomous functionality. Therefore, functionalities for perception based on sensors such as LiDARs, cameras and IMUs have been developed to implement the autonomous functions that support the inspection robots in the PILOTING platform.

This deliverable is the direct outcome of the work performed within tasks T5.2 (“Dexterous manipulation from ground vehicles”) and T5.4 (“Perception and intelligent navigation for ground robots and crawlers”).

1.2 Structure of the document

This document is organized into three main sections. Section 2 describes the architecture and algorithmic modules developed to detect and manipulate the hand wheels on valves. This section is specific to the UGV manipulator use case and summarizes the work performed in task T5.2. Section 3 addresses the advanced perception and autonomous navigation modules developed in task T5.4. The ground robotic vehicles have different morphology and are equipped with different sensors and placement layouts, making the implementation robot specific. Each subsection recaps the sensing capability of the platform and describes the specific implementation for each ground robot with the updates from the beta version. Finally, Section 4 presents some conclusions of the work performed in the tasks.

2. Algorithms for Dexterous Manipulation

For the refinery scenario a UGV has been equipped with grippers to have the means to execute maintenance tasks. In this section the solution for perception and control is described, more details of the beta version can be found in D5.2.

The task that is being addressed is manipulation of valves, which is a useful capability that is not supported by currently commercially available robots for refineries. Since the handwheels on the valves are all designed for human workers, this robot needs to be designed taking into account the physical constraints that this implies, in order to not damage the assets of the refinery, or the robot itself.

2.1 Scenario description

In the context of this chapter, the UGV is located in a typical, quasi-static industrial refinery environment. As a prerequisite for precise dexterous manipulation tasks, it is assumed that the prior location of all assets that are to be manipulated, as well as the type of these respective assets, such as valves, are known in the map. This is a reasonable and valid assumption, since plans of asset types and locations usually already exist within the refinery infrastructure documentation or digital building information model (BIM). Therefore, it is only a matter of transforming these locations to the digital twin of the refinery that is created throughout the mapping process. Also, if further properties about assets exist, these can be incorporated into the digital twin. For example, in the case of valves, the radius, number of spokes and expected torque range can be valuable information. With this information, the manipulation can be carried out more robustly, since misdetections can be ruled out with a higher degree of certainty using all of the provided information. The more of this information is provided within the digital plan of the refinery, the more robust and safe the overall operation can be executed. However, since in practice it might not be desired or economically feasible to populate the digital model with all of these properties upfront, our manipulation strategy can also cope with uncertainties and a reduced amount of information. In the context of valves, the minimal baseline for successful manipulation is merely the location of the asset within the plant and all further information is kept as optional parameters. This means that even with minimal upfront effort, the dexterous manipulation pipeline can be run, which allows for a low entry barrier and a smooth, gradual and cost-effective adoption phase at new plants.

Once the locations of assets to be manipulated is determined, it is up to the refinery operator to specify the exact properties of the manipulation task. This is done in the context of inspection mission planning. At each valve that is to be manipulated, an inspection waypoint is set. The inspection point needs to be populated with the information of the overall turning angle and turning direction for the respective valve.

With all parameters set, the manipulation mission can be uploaded and carried out autonomously by the robot. It is to highlight that no further intervention by the operator is required at this time. This is the point where our solution starts to become cost-saving for the operator. Since the setup and manipulation plan creation is usually only required at the very beginning of the installation of the

system and only small modifications may be done afterwards, operators can focus more on high-level tasks and the manual effort required by the operator in the long-term is reduced greatly.

Throughout the mission execution, all relevant data, such as robot telemetry, manipulator state, joint torques and end-effector force are captured. Also, warnings and errors occurring throughout the manipulation process are recorded in order to be visualized. This allows the operator to gain precise insights into both the state of the robot and the plant. Overall, this allows the operator to improve the autonomous missions carried out by the robot over time, as well as detect and catch errors or deviations from the digital model early on.

In the following sections, the individual software components required to provide this overall functionality are presented.

2.2 High level overview and architecture

The valve manipulation problem requires first perceiving the 3D pose of the valve. Once the 3D pose of the valve has been successfully extracted from the scene, a dynamic grasp strategy is deployed according to the relative position between the manipulator and the asset. After a successful grasp, a manipulation plan is generated based on simple motion primitives. The generated end effector trajectory is tracked by an arm-level controller. The deployed control method consists of a compliant cartesian control scheme with feedforward gravity and Coriolis compensation. Due to its reactive properties, the control scheme can successfully handle slight misdetections or misalignments of the gripper with respect to the asset.

2.3 Perception for valve manipulation

It is assumed that an approximate knowledge of the valve location in a previously generated global map is available. The navigation pipeline is then in charge of bringing the valve into the field of view of the manipulator. The Intel RealSense RGB-D camera mounted at the wrist (eye-in-hand) is then used to provide the visual input for the detection algorithm. In particular, a combination of a learning method and more traditional template matching for object detection is deployed. In the first step, the RGB image is passed through a deep CNN, which outputs valve's keypoints. The valve's keypoints are identified as the intersection points between the valve handwheel and the spokes that connect it to the shaft, see Figure 1. An autonomous data collection pipeline has been developed to provide labeled training data efficiently and with little user intervention. This allows us to collect a rich dataset under various lighting conditions and different valve models. Furthermore, the use of keypoints generalizes better under intra-category variations (e. g. various handwheel shapes and visual appearances, various number of spokes). The keypoints are projected to 3D space using the data from the depth channel of the RGB-D camera. In contrast to the depth estimation by triangulation using the ZED mini presented in D5.2, this results in more accurate overall depth estimates, as the stereo disparity was not large enough to deliver robust estimates. Once the keypoint positions are known, a 3D model of the valve is fit, see Figure 2. Prior information about the valve diameter, handle radius, spoke size and spoke count can be incorporated to allow for robust error detection. In this case, the valve detection process is repeated multiple times using different poses of the robot end-effector until

the maximum residual error between the positions of the keypoints on the fitted 3D model and the actual keypoint positions detected by the camera is below a predefined threshold.

In contrast to the valve fitting approach presented in D5.2 which was based on a prior, precise point cloud model of the valve for the ICP object registration process, our new approach does not require an exact knowledge of the valve's shape and properties, featuring a much better generalization over a larger variety of different valves.

Figure 1. Typical detections of keypoints on hand wheel valves by the UGV in the refinery.

Figure 2. Detected valve pose relative to UGV.

2.4 Trajectory planning and compliant valve manipulation

This manipulation task requires interaction with a stiff environment under imperfect sensing and state estimate. Therefore, we deploy a cartesian impedance control strategy. In contrast to the admittance control scheme presented in D5.2, this method can achieve much lower latency of the controller when reacting to external forces. This means that potential collisions with rigid objects in the environment can be handled faster and more efficiently, which increases the overall system safety. For this module, we use an adapted version of the built-in Franka arm impedance controller. The adaptations include a split of the gains in cartesian end-effector space, such that the robot operates more stiffly along the turning axis of the valve, while still remaining compliant along the orthogonal axes, reacting to potential disturbances or misdetections.

Once the valve pose is known, the turning trajectory is generated by a sampling-based motion planner, running a cost-based optimization scheme which takes into account the position and width of the spokes and the robot's end-effector, as illustrated in Figure 3. The costs are computed in a way that incentivizes the planner to avoid reaching the robot's joint limits, collisions between the robot and the valve, and self-collisions of the robot itself.

Figure 3. Valve model-based motion planning – generated trajectory.

The execution of the manipulation mission is managed by a state machine. The state transition logic accounts for feasibility of the manipulation plan and makes sure that manipulation with a fixed base is triggered once the arm is in the valve reach. It also dynamically handles the requests sent by the operator of the gRCS. For example, the capturing of photos can be manually triggered during the mission at any time.

During the execution of the valve manipulation mission, the force at the end-effector is continuously recorded over time, as shown in Figure 4. This allows for very detailed introspection capabilities into the manipulation process and the current state of every asset. Especially physical effects such as wear can be monitored and documented over multiple missions. This also enables the refinery operator to schedule preventive maintenance procedures entirely based on measured data.

Figure 4. Force measured at the end-effector during one valve manipulation action.

The entire autonomous detection and manipulation pipeline was successfully verified during the refinery experiments, photos from the experiments can be seen in Figure 5 and Figure 6. It is to remark that no critical errors requiring manual user intervention occurred and no damage to neither the asset, nor the robot has been incurred throughout all experiments.

Figure 5. Autonomous valve detection in refinery environment.

Figure 6. UGV manipulating the detected hand-wheel valve by a predetermined angle.

2.5 Experimental results

The presented manipulation algorithms were successfully verified in a real-world refinery scenario. After uploading the manipulation targets to the robot, the robot was able to detect a hand-wheel valve in 3D space. It was then able to manipulate the valve by turning it by a predefined angle. Throughout the mission, all relevant manipulation feedback was successfully recorded.

It has been shown that the developed pipeline is highly robust and delivers reproducible results. The entire manipulation mission has been repeated more than 5 times in total. The presented outlier rejection strategy based on the residual projection errors was proven to be very successful and highly relevant. Even in the case a valve was not detected or grasped successfully in the first attempt, the operation could be automatically repeated without manual intervention in all of the experiments. Without this rejection strategy, a wrongly fitted valve would not have been detected in multiple cases and thus in the worst-case scenario, the mission could have returned a success even though the valve was not manipulated at all.

Since the cartesian compliance controller was active during manipulation, no damage to the robot or the asset was caused during the actual trajectory execution phases. This would not have been possible without damage if the prior admittance controller would have been deployed, since the delay for it to react to collisions would have been too high in the context of the stiff, metallic assets.

Conclusively, all missions have been completed successfully. It is to highlight that the feedback from involved refinery stakeholders was consistently positive. Overall, it could be shown that the developed dexterous manipulation algorithms present a highly effective, usable and inherently safe strategy for refinery operators to automate critical or repetitive manipulation tasks.

3. Perception and Intelligent Navigation

In this chapter the perception and navigation solutions for ground robots are described including both hardware and software. There are three different scenarios with different robots, the CART for tunnel navigation, the BIKE for vessel and tank inspection and for the refinery scenario outside of vessels the RISING and the UGV robot platform of ETHZ.

Common for these navigation solutions are that they are based on onboard sensors and onboard processing that allow the robots to operate autonomously. This reduces the need for external infrastructure and communication. However, it increases the requirement on computing power and makes the selection of sensors critical to achieve the navigation requirements with a reasonable energy consumption and component cost.

The inspection missions are provided from the PILOTING I&M platform, where they have been planned using a 3D map. The map may either be created from existing models, or they can be generated by the PILOTING inspection robots. The alignment to the global position reference system is less important in the cases where inspection is taking place in confined spaces, such as vessels, and to some degree tunnels. It is more important that the 3D maps shall be consistent over time, so that it is possible to localize and monitor possible changes of the state of defects and assets of interest.

3.1 Refinery Navigation

In D5.2 the general refinery navigation was described in more detail with the RISING platform as example. While the current section focuses on the UGV, the same algorithms can also be run on the RISING platform.

The UGV is an all-terrain skid-steered 4-wheeled robot equipped with a 3D LiDAR, visual-inertial tracking camera, wheel encoders, and onboard computing. The navigation stack is tailored to large industrial environments such as refineries, which motivates the assumptions that the environment does not change often and is only shared with cooperative agents and humans. In terms of sensors, the navigation algorithms assume that a high resolution 3D LiDAR and an IMU is always available. Note that these can typically be purchased as a single device, such as the Ouster OS0-128. Some parts of the stack also fuse in information from odometry tracking cameras such as the Intel T265, depth cameras such as the Intel D455 and wheel odometry. However, all of these inputs are flexible in terms of hardware choice and often optional.

Figure 7. Overview of the UGV and some of the environments in which it was tested in context of PILOTING. In the image on the left, the UGV can be seen together with its LiDAR sensor mounted in front of the arm and the Intel T265 tracking camera on the robot's torso. The images on the right feature different indoor and outdoor Search and Rescue sites across Switzerland with features resembling industrial sites. Images of the real industrial facilities inspected for PILOTING are not shown due to confidentiality.

3.1.1 Localization and Mapping

The localization and mapping pipeline of the robot is run in two modes. In the first mode, the robot performs LiDAR-inertial Simultaneous Localization and Mapping. This mode is typically used while driving the robot around the facilities under teleoperation. Alternatively, a human operator can scan the plant by hand using a single LiDAR-inertial sensor, such as an Ouster OS1, and a laptop or lightweight computer. Given recent advances in LiDAR sensors and LiDAR-inertial odometry, the global maps resulting from FastLIO2 [1] exceeded the necessary quality and accuracy in all performed experiments. Note that FastLIO2 does not explicitly detect global loop closures and apply corresponding global map deformations. Although it turned out not to be necessary in the environments tested thus far, a pipeline was developed to incorporate global loop closure corrections in Open3D SLAM [2] if needed. The resulting precise, dense 3D point cloud map of the environment can then be used to plan subsequent inspection and manipulation missions. The main difference with respect to D5.2 is that the mapping module no longer requires a visual-inertial input. Removing reliance on time synchronized cameras reduces the need for specialized hardware and intrinsic and extrinsic calibration. Furthermore, by virtue of being active sensors LiDARs are insensitive to illumination changes and most weather conditions. Finally, the system no longer depends on maplab [3], an optimization-based visual-inertial SLAM system, which reduces computational requirements.

Figure 8. Image of a pre-built map for missions in a refinery environment, recorded using a single Ouster OS1-64 LiDAR sensor and its integrated IMU.

In the second mode, the robot localizes itself in the pre-built map to execute the planned missions. Robustness to different surface and lighting conditions is obtained by fusing wheel and visual-inertial odometry, in combination with global point cloud registration to eliminate drift. On the UGV robot, the optional visual-inertial odometry is obtained from an Intel T265 tracking camera. The global point cloud registration is performed using ICP as implemented by libpointmatcher (<https://github.com/ethz-asl/libpointmatcher>). All the estimates are fused using an Extended Kalman Filter, as implemented by the MSF package (https://github.com/ethz-asl/ethzasl_msf). The main changes since D5.2 are that the visual-inertial odometry is now optional and offloaded to the Intel T265 sensor, reducing the requirements in terms of calibration and specialized hardware, given that the T265 input is optional and several alternatives exist. Furthermore, the various pose inputs are no longer fused using sliding window optimization, as formerly done by ConFusion [4], reducing the robot's computational load.

Figure 9. Illustration of localization and navigation in a pre-built map of a Search and Rescue training site featuring a large dome. The sensor view on the right shows the point clouds used for global registration and the navigation cost map superimposed on the pre-built global point cloud map.

3.1.2 Motion Planning and Control

The motion planning is divided into a global and a local planning phase. The definition of inspection locations in the IVP and the subsequent creation of inspection points in the gRCS enables the global motion planning for the UGV. In particular, the defined inspection points are considered as waypoints for the planner running on the UGV.

Using the pre-built map as a basis, the global navigation is done by means of an RRT* planner. It finds the shortest path from the UGV's current position to the next mission waypoint while considering obstacles in the pre-built map and the robot's footprint. The global planner assumes that the environment is static, but supports traversability annotations that can for example be used to mark dangerous areas, invisible obstacles or areas where the ground is not safe to drive on as untraversable. The local planner translates the global plan into safe local trajectories that: (1) avoid collisions with newly encountered obstacles in addition to the obstacles of the pre-built map, (2) stay close to the global path while allowing for small detours (e.g. around displaced equipment or dynamic obstacles including humans), and (3) ensures that only kino-dynamically feasible trajectories are sent to the

controller. These requirements are met by using an online optimal local time elastic band (TEB) planner. Our experiments show that the TEB planner effectively and safely follows coarse paths from the global planner, while avoiding dynamic, local obstacles and effectively negotiating small differences between the pre-built map and the robot's real surroundings. Furthermore, the experiments show that by explicitly considering the UGV's skid-steer constraints, the TEB planner generates trajectories that are feasible and can accurately be followed. The motion planning and control pipeline conceptually remained close to what was discussed in D5.2, and most of the work in this area consisted of refinements, usability and performance enhancements. However, the trajectories from TEB can now directly be sent to the robot platform's low level controller. Since an intermediate MPC controller is no longer required, the navigation stack is now easier to maintain, tune, and more robust in practice.

3.2 Vessel Inspection

Inspection of vessels and tanks require specialized robots that can move around the metal walls in confined spaces. The navigation requires special solutions in order to support the inspection without the need for human inspectors to enter the vessels. While the BIKE started as a manually, remotely operated robot, the development in PILOTING has now enabled autonomous operation. Integration with the PILOTING I&M platform allows the inspection missions planned in the IVP and gRCS to be executed by the BIKE. The integrated solution allows the plant/asset owner or operator to plan inspections based on asset management tools and considering the relevant codes, previous inspections as well as risk-based inspection plans. The autonomy of BIKE, achieved by integration with gRCS, enables the inspector to execute the inspection in a reliable way, ensuring not pre-planned tasks were omitted. BIKE will move from planned task execution to planned task execution and allow the inspector to focus on the data collection.

3.2.1 BIKE

The BIKE robot is a magnetic crawler moving on metal surfaces inside pressure vessels and other similarly confined spaces. The BIKE localization and control system was already described in D5.2 in section 3.2.

For the PILOTING solution, eventually a new compact 3D LIDAR was developed and integrated on the BIKE following the schematic already presented in D5.2 (Figure 1515).

Figure 10 shows the 3D LIDAR mounted on the BIKE. As depicted in D4.3, section 4.1.2. The 3D LIDAR is basically a rotating 2D LIDAR unit of slightly higher resolution as used previously for localization.

Figure 10. BIKE integrated 3D LIDAR.

3.2.2 Localization and Mapping

The localization system described in D5.2 was adapted to process the data generated by the new 3D LIDAR solution. The main difference is that a full 3D point cloud is available instead of just points on a 2D plane. The 3D data provides much higher reliability for positioning the robot in the environment. However, the acquisition time of a full point cloud is larger due to the slow scanning movement. While scanning time has no impact on the robot speed or the inspection duration, it is purely internal to the localization system, however it had to be incorporated in the localization solution it had to be incorporated in the localization solution. Testing in lab and field environments was successful. Figure 11 shows some of the accuracy experiments performed during field trials. The largest error observed was within the model uncertainty.

Figure 11. Localization by rotating LIDAR on BIKE verified by camera pointing at features (such as nozzles).

The 3D LIDAR also allows for mapping of the environment. In a first step, individual point clouds were collected during the field trials, Figure 12. Eventually, a registration solution was implemented,

which allows for on-the-go point cloud registration while the BIKE is moving around the environment. A preliminary version of this tool chain was successfully tested in a lab environment and will be extensively verified in the upcoming field trials. Once the testing is successful, this method will be available to generate models for mission planning.

Figure 12. Registered 3D pointcloud data from BIKE (constructed from individual point clouds collected during field trials).

3.2.3 Motion Planning and Control

The motion planning and control was implemented as already laid out in D5.2.

The inspection locations are planned in the PILOTING portal asset management. For each asset, inspection plans are generated in the portal, which basically assign tasks to inspection locations and a designated (suggested) sequence of task execution. The inspection plan is downloaded to gRCS together with the asset model. The inspector uses gRCS to create a detailed mission plan, linking the tasks (in the suggested order or in an adjusted one), with the possibility of adding waypoints for the robot to pass through. The resulting waypoint list (waypoints and tasks) is transmitted to the BIKE control software, where the path planner attempts to create feasible paths for the BIKE. In case the planner is unsuccessful (i.e. if the planned waypoints are impossible to reach), the operator needs to refine the waypoint list either in the gRCS or directly in the BIKE control software.

A structured pre-processing of the environment model is used to obtain a map in the form of a set of connected voxels. In a first step, a set of voxels close enough to any surface is generated.

The voxel set is later segmented into continuous regions based on transition conditions on the surfaces. Figure 13 shows the result of the automated edge-analysis used to determine if the transition from one surface triangle to the next is possible. Based on this edge classification the voxel set is split into connected regions as shown in Figure 14. Each region is assumed to be connected for BIKE operations.

Figure 13. Edges classification by crossability, red edges are considered un-crossable by the BIKE.

Figure 14. Admissible voxels: map of connected sets, connected sets are indicated by color.

For any given start- and end-voxel from the same connected set, the voxel map is then used to generate a feasible path for the BIKE, as illustrated in Figure 15. The path planner basically applies A* on the

voxel set to obtain the shortest feasible path. In a second step, the path is checked for collisions. The collision checker places a vehicle bounding box at subsampled path locations with correct orientation, assuming good path-following performance. If a voxel from another connected region than the one on which the planning is executed intersects with the bounding box, a collision is assumed. In case a collision is found, the voxels causing the collision are removed from the admissible set and the A* is executed again. The process is repeated until either a collision-free path is found, or all paths are blocked by collisions.

Figure 15. Path planned from start and end point in same set of admissible voxels.

Figure 16. Path execution for inspection mission, including multiple points of interest as well as raster-path segment.

3.2.4 Obstacle Detection

Once a path is found, the BIKE can autonomously execute it in a safe way (as in the example inspection shown by Figure 16) unless either the localization system fails, the environment model is not accurate or foreign objects are encountered. In all such cases, the BIKE should detect any resulting unmapped obstacles in its path and stop immediately.

Multiple approaches to reliably detect obstacles in the 3D pointcloud data coming from the on-board LIDAR were evaluated. Eventually and after many tests, a filter based on calculated surface normals proved very reliable in the lab environments. Figure 17 shows how obstacles get correctly separated from the driving surface.

Figure 17. Obstacle detection in relevant lab environments. Blue equals points on the “driving surface”, other colors represent detected obstacles.

3.3 Tunnel Inspection

The tunnel inspection will be done in two different phases, a general inspection and a local inspection. In the general inspection, the CART UGV will drive through the tunnel and collect inspection data using its onboard inspection sensors. From this data it will be determined where there is a need for more detailed inspection of defects and other points of interest. The CART will then return to those places and carry out a detailed inspection where inspection data can be collected at close distance, for example using the TT drone and an arm mounted camera. Both the general and the local missions will be provided by the PILOTING I&M platform. The local inspection can therefore be prepared based on the analysis of the data from the general inspection, and the position coordinates of the CART where the TT drone has the landing platform will serve as a reference for the TT drone in the local inspection. Hence, the same map will be used for planning both the general and the local inspection. The CART navigation payload can generate this map, or it can be provided from other sources. Once the map is available, the main requirement of the CART is that it can navigate within the existing map and re-localize points of interest with an accuracy better than 10 cm.

3.3.1 CART

The CART is an autonomous ground vehicle that will be used for tunnel inspection with an inspection camera mounted on an arm, a scanning LiDAR for inspection, and a UAV on the roof which can be used for detailed inspection with photos taken up close to points of interest. As it will mainly operate inside the tunnel, it will not have access to GNSS and needs to rely on other means for navigation.

Therefore, the CART is equipped with a navigation payload with sensors and computing resources dedicated to localization and mapping in tunnels.

The motion planning and motion control is implemented in the CART's onboard computer, and further supported by a safety LiDAR mounted at the front of the vehicle for collision avoidance. The localization and mapping functionality in the navigation payload is integrated with the motion planning and control through an Ethernet interface where ROS messages are exchanged.

3.3.2 Localization and Mapping

The navigation payload consists of three sensors: a 3D LiDAR, a camera and an IMU. These are the same as in the beta version of the payload. However, the hardware has been significantly modified to improve its robustness, and is now mounted in a protective metal box as can be seen in Figure 18. This is based on the experience of several hardware components breaking during testing of the beta version. In the process, the solution has also been simplified.

Figure 18. The navigation payload seen from different angles.

The first version of the navigation payload contained a Raspberry Pi that was used to collect synchronization signals and time stamp sensor data. Since two of these broke during tests and the supply at the time was very limited, it was decided to redesign and simplify the payload without the use of any Raspberry Pi. The NUC now performs the actions of the Raspberry Pi that are needed for the SLAM algorithms in use.

To synchronize the sensor data, the Lidar generates the PTP timestamp and the trigger signal at the beginning of each Lidar scan. When the camera receives the trigger signal, it acquires a frame. Data from all sensors are then collected and time-aligned in the NUC. Since the Lidar is the only sensor

with native PTP support, its timestamp is used as the reference for data from the IMU and camera. This is such that the previous LiDAR frame adjusted for the time of the frame acquisition (100 ms) is used to timestamp the next Lidar frame, IMU and camera data, as illustrated in Figure 19. This is needed since the camera and IMU data from the same timeslot arrives before the data and timestamp from the Lidar. This method thus makes it possible to synchronize data from all three sensors with identical timestamps, which is needed for some of the algorithms that are currently in use. For validation purposes, the LiDAR, camera and IMU topics containing adjusted timestamps are published on new topics suffixed with ‘_sync’.

Figure 19. Time synchronization of LiDAR, camera and IMU.

The components required for navigation are an Intel NUC (as the onboard computer), Ouster OS0-128-U LiDAR, FLIR BFS-U3-17S7M-C camera with Kowa LM6HC 1/1.8 lens with IR filter, an Xsens Mti-630 IMU and a router. These are mounted in an aluminum casing that provides protection and convenient attachment possibilities. In addition, the power supply has been improved by adding a DC/DC converter such that the payload can handle input power with different voltage levels and improve the voltage quality to minimize the risk of components breaking. The navigation payload does not include any light source, hence it relies on sufficient lighting from the vehicle or from light sources in the tunnel. Moreover, it does not have any GNSS receiver, since it is only designed for navigation inside the tunnel. Therefore, the alignment between the localization within the tunnel with the global position would need to be done by the robot platform at the entrances of the tunnel, if such alignment is required in the asset management system.

The shipping container was purchased and customized to protect components while in transportation. The dimensions and total weight of 17 kg are suitable for air transport.

Figure 20. Transportation casing.

3.3.2.1 SLAM software

The SLAM solution is based on LOAM – Lidar Odometry and Mapping in real-time [5]. This combines an odometry thread that computes the motion of the LiDAR between sweeps with a mapping thread that incrementally builds a map from the point cloud and computes the pose of the LiDAR in the map. Initially, we experimented using LIO-SAM, a LiDAR-inertial odometry solution to provide state estimates. This solution did at times provide a high degree of accuracy, but we also experienced that the solution lacked robustness, and at times state estimates would spiral off due to faulty IMU integration. As robustness is a priority, we transitioned to a LiDAR-only SLAM solution and expanded on this by adding additional constraints from the camera and from the cart's wheel odometry to the state estimates.

The lidar based estimate of the robot pose in a tunnel is well constrained in five out of six degrees of freedom, namely the rotational components and the translation in the height and width dimensions of the tunnel. However, the translation along the traveling axis of the tunnel will drift as the geometry of each scan along this axis will be more or less identical. To fix this degeneracy in the state estimation the camera is used to add non-geometric features that constrain the optimization also along the degenerate axis. Two types of visual features are used:

- ORB features [6] are extracted per scan and added as additional constraints in both the scan matching performed in the odometry thread and in the mapping thread. These features are considered only locally unique and are thus only used to improve motion estimates locally. These might be extracted from light fixtures, road markings, signs, and markings on the tunnel wall.
- ArUco features are extracted whenever they are available and are added to the scan matching in the mapping thread. ArUco features are considered globally unique and can thus be used to correct for drift in the motion estimate when the robot is visiting a place it has seen before, or when localizing in an existing map.

As we need the 3D coordinates of the visual features to use them as constraints in scan matching, we project the LiDAR cloud into the image, and find the depth of each visual feature from these transformed LiDAR points. An illustration of the results can be seen in Figure 21.

Figure 21. Cart pose (red arrow), surface features (pink dots), ORB features (smaller red / blue squares) and ArUco features (large blue cubes) projected into the point cloud.

Wheel odometry has also been added as an optional input to the algorithm. Initially, this was used as a correction if a degeneracy was detected on the translation part of the pose estimate. Degeneracy detection was performed by analyzing the covariance matrix of the state estimate in the mapping thread. In the new version, the wheel odometry from the cart can instead be added as an optional constraint in the scan matching performed in the mapping thread. The wheel odometry can be considered as a redundancy in the system and will contribute to constraining the translation along the traveling distance of the tunnel in case a sufficiently large set of visual features is not available.

Furthermore, during testing it was found that the network traffic between the navigation payload and the CART onboard computer was causing performance problems that occasionally lead to loss of data and sensor synchronization when the PTP packets were lost or delayed excessively. This mainly appears to be due to interrupts triggered by UDP packets arriving, which is causing scheduling problems on the receiving computer. Therefore, a significant optimization of the communication has been made, where the number of ROS topics that are published is minimized.

3.3.2.2 System overview

An overview of the system can be seen in Figure 22. The LiDAR cloud is undistorted by integrating up the IMU's gyro since the last scan and thus finding the robot's rotation during the scan period. This compensates for the robot's movement during the acquisition of the LiDAR scan.

After this, surface features are extracted from the LiDAR scan.

In parallel, ArUco features and ORB features are extracted from the current image. These features are projected into 3D by sampling the LiDAR cloud for depths.

Following this, scan-to-scan matching is performed in the odometry thread, matching surface features and ORB features from the previous and the current scan to estimate the relative motion between scans.

Motion estimates from the odometry thread as well as surface, ORB and ArUco features are passed on to the mapping thread. Here, scan-to-map matching is performed to align the current LiDAR data to the map.

After scan-to-map matching is successful, all incoming point features are added to the map.

Figure 22. A schematic of the localization and mapping algorithm. Ceres is the optimization framework that is used in the ICP scan matching.

3.3.3 Motion Planning

The motion planning in the tunnel is seemingly simple, since it is enough to follow the car lane to the waypoints provided in the mission plan. Hence, standard ROS packages were used as a basis for the beta version of the CART motion planning. The planners also use real-time information to update grid maps for obstacle avoidance. In addition, there is a safety laser scanner on the front of the vehicle, which will stop the vehicle in case an object occurs unexpectedly. Since it is assumed that this is a rare event and it may not be safe to navigate around an obstacle in a tunnel with traffic in another lane, the CART will not replan and start autonomously after it is stopped by the safety laser scanner. A more detailed description of the motion planning can be found in D5.2.

The first tests revealed that special care was needed to keep a constant distance to the tunnel wall in order to get high-quality inspection data. For this reason, a different planner is now used when a general inspection needs to be done. This specific planner provides a way to navigate while following the tunnel wall at a fixed distance and speed. This is useful in order to cover a larger area and capture data while moving. The link between the localization and the triggering of the inspection payload is also taken into account in this planner.

3.3.4 Motion Control

The general motion of the CART is controlled by directly modifying the commands sent to its motor controller, in combination with a power steering system that has been added to the vehicle. This has been described in D5.2.

One main update from the beta version has been required to better handle the challenging steep slopes in the drainage tunnel. An enhanced version of the robot controller has been deployed. The robot is now comparing the inclination published by the robot IMU and then mapping it to a certain low-level configuration, where different PID controllers are tuned in order to provide different control actions for the motor. This also helps to keep speed references and hold positions whenever the robot is on a certain slope.

3.3.5 *Experimental results*

A current requirement of the system is that it requires ArUco markers to be installed in the tunnel. When testing the system on site, these were placed roughly at 20-meter intervals throughout the tunnel stretch. The ArUco markers help to limit the drift of the localization along the length of the tunnel and allow the system to quickly localize when using a pre-built map. Thus, when navigating in an existing map, any error in localization will be corrected whenever a tag is detected effectively capping the drift.

The full system has been exposed to scenarios in two instances, first in a drainage and a road tunnel located close to Metsovo, Greece in the autumn of 2022, and later in an old railway tunnel outside Coripe, Spain during the spring 2023.

Figure 23. Example images from road tunnel, Metsovo, and old train tunnel, Coripe.

During tests in the tunnel in **Metsovo**, we experienced several technical issues with data acquisition. We also lack ground truth data of the CART's pose, thus a proper evaluation of the system was not possible to make. What can be evaluated is the precision of the system's ability to perform mapping,

by comparing the distance between the two furthest tags in the tunnel over several runs. The results of this evaluation can be seen in Figure 24.

Figure 24. The estimated length of the tunnel segment from the 8 data recordings in the road tunnel, with and without using the wheel odometry as an additional constraint.

One can see that the differences in estimated length between the two farthest tags is consistently estimated to be around 126 meters (+/- 1 meter), apart from the estimates based on *dataset 3*. It is worth noting that the data in *take 3*, was recorded when the lights or the cart were turned off, and we see that the system at times struggles to track visual features. The updates described in the previous sections improve the performance in lab tests, but still need to be validated in a real tunnel.

Moreover, further tests were performed in **Coripe, Spain**. These tests were done after a large upgrade and we experienced that the payload produce continuous and well synchronized data. At this site we also had the benefit of being able to record a few datasets while simultaneously recording the position of the CART UGV with a Leica robotic total station tracking a prism mounted on top of the LIDAR. The total station will only capture the CART's position, but reports this with sub centimeter precision at 10Hz, and can thus be considered as a ground truth to evaluate the system against.

As we did not have time to synchronize the clocks and align the frames between the total station and the CART vehicle before recording datasets, this was done after the fact by cross correlating the trajectories and then aligning frames by Umeyama's [7] method.

In addition to using the data from the total station as a source of positional ground truth, we have also made allowance for the system to utilize the aligned total station position as an additional constraint, thus allowing for a theoretical sub centimeter precision when building a map of the tunnel. By this method we built the map that was used to evaluate localization performance in the following experiments, see Figure 25.

Figure 25. A map of the Coripe tunnel, 175m long.

We have in total three datasets from which we can evaluate the accuracy of the system. The system will be evaluated both when performing mapping and when we are localizing in an existing map. About the three datasets, the first set is a roundtrip in the tunnel at inspection speed with only the tunnel lights used as illumination. The second dataset is recorded under the same conditions but with a much higher speed. And the third dataset contains a single forward pass with the CART's headlights switched on.

As an evaluation framework we have used TUMs evo package for comparison of trajectory output of SLAM algorithms [8].

Table 1. Mapping absolute position error vs total station, in meters.

	slow_rt_dark	fast_rt_dark	fast_sp_light
max err.	1.091494	0.627485	1.213169
mean err.	0.538306	0.263727	0.319566
median err.	0.531237	0.248052	0.286404

Figure 26. Mapping absolute position error vs total station for the three different data sets.

Table 2. Localization in a priori map, absolute position error vs total station, in meters.

	slow_rt_dark	fast_rt_dark	fast_sp_light
max err.	0.286804	0.752042	0.373815
mean err.	0.074086	0.115463	0.094367
median err.	0.060949	0.087059	0.070951

Figure 27. Localization in a priori map, absolute position error vs total station for the three different data sets.

The performance measured as absolute position error can be seen in Table 1 for the mapping experiments and in Table 2 for the localization in an existing map. The progression of the absolute error over time can be seen in Figure 26 the mapping runs and Figure 27 for the localization runs. Comparing the APE of the mapping runs versus the localization runs a couple of observations can be made. Firstly, localizing in an existing map has a positive effect on max error, as well as average and median error. This is reasonable as a preexisting map allows the system to correct for drift when observing a global landmark. Secondly, we are still above the goal of 10 cm maximum error when localizing in a preexisting map. The accuracy of the system has been greatly increased compared to the version that was tested in Metsovo, and through further work we might still improve on this, but in real world scenarios, there will likely be situations and conditions that can give the occasional error larger than this criterion.

4. Conclusions

This document describes how the autonomous functionalities for the ground robots and crawlers have been developed into their final version based on the experience from the first experiments in the refinery and in the Metsovo tunnels. The experiments provided valuable insights into which solutions worked well, but also revealed some limitations, and improvements have been made to address those.

With regards to the manipulation tasks in refineries, the UGV hardware and software have been updated to adapt to different valve designs which makes the system easier to deploy in new environments. The control also reacts faster, which improves the safety of the system. The solution is working very well with these improvements and fulfills the requirements as planned.

For the navigation of ground robots in the refinery scenario, the solution has been improved in several ways. For example, the mapping and localization no longer requires visual-inertial odometry and the motion control no longer relies on an intermediate MPC controller. However, the main concept has remained the same as in the Beta version, since it proved to work well.

The BIKE crawler's 2D LiDAR has been successfully replaced with a 3D LIDAR, and the software has been updated accordingly. Furthermore, different obstacle detection methods have been evaluated and an effective solution has been selected.

For the tunnel scenario, the main updates have been on the navigation payload, which has been redesigned for better robustness of both the hardware and the SLAM solution that now has better filters to select the features to include. In addition, communication bottlenecks between the navigation payload and the CART have been identified and addressed. By comparing estimated trajectories with a ground truth, we have assessed the accuracy of the system to be generally very high, but we still observe that the error at times surpass 10cm. Further efforts to reduce these, through better calibration routines and data association will be considered.

All the autonomous solutions for the ground and crawler robots are now undergoing final testing to be ready for the final demonstration campaign in the last months of PILOTING. In general, good performance that fulfills the requirements has been achieved. The autonomous functionalities have also been integrated with the rest of the PILOTING platform, such as the gRCS and the IVP, both to produce the 3D maps and to receive and execute missions autonomously.

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